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DISTANCE EDUCATION AND DIGITAL INCLUSION: CONTRIBUTIONS AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the relationship between Distance Education (DE) and digital inclusion. The literature review revealed that distance learning provides access to education for different social groups, but digital inclusion is crucial. Limited internet access and a lack of digital skills were challenges identified. It was recommended to invest in connectivity infrastructure, digital training programs and electronic devices. In addition, addressing inequalities and promoting partnerships between educational and government institutions is key. The conclusion emphasizes the importance of digital inclusion for equal opportunities in distance learning, seeking an inclusive and equitable education. Overcoming the challenges identified will contribute to full student participation. In summary, this research highlights the need for targeted policies and strategies to promote digital inclusion in distance learning, with a view to the participation of all students.